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THE IMPACT OF ACCOUNTING BASIS AND APPLIED FINANCIAL REPORTING FRAMEWORK ON THE CORRUPTION PERCEPTION INDEX IN THE PUBLIC SECTOR

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Abstract

This paper investigates the impact of different accounting bases and financial reporting frameworks on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) in the public sector. Specifically, it examines how various accounting approaches (cash, modified cash, accrual, and modified accrual) and reporting frameworks (national accounting standards, International Public Sector Accounting Standards-IPSAS with or without modifications, and other frameworks) influence the perception of corruption in public institutions. The study uses a sample of 147 countries, with the CPI as the dependent variable and accounting basis and financial reporting framework as independent variables. The results of the ANOVA analysis reveal a statistically significant difference in corruption perception indices among countries employing different accounting bases. The results of this study indicate that countries applying simpler accounting frameworks, such as national standards and IPSAS modified for the local context, show a lower perception of corruption, as evidenced by a higher CPI value. In contrast, more complex frameworks, including IPSAS or national standards referencing IPSAS, combined with cash and partial accrual bases, do not significantly reduce corruption perception. Additionally, countries using national standards based on IFRS exhibit the lowest levels of perceived corruption in the public sector.

Keywords: Accounting Basis, Financial Reporting Framework, Corruption Perceptions Index, Public Sector

1. Introduction

This study aims to determine the impact of different accounting frameworks for financial reporting, along with various bases of recording business events, on the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI) in the public sector. We analyze whether the use of cash basis, modified cash basis, accrual basis, or modified accrual basis, together with different reporting frameworks—such as national accounting standards or IPSAS—affects the level of corruption perception in public institutions. This research will address whether reforming a country's accounting system can contribute to reducing corruption perception in the public sector.

The accounting framework and basis on which financial reporting is grounded differ across countries worldwide. In the profit sector, a significant number of countries—156 in total—use or allow financial reporting in compliance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) set by the International Federation of Accountants (IFAC). These standards have been developed since the 1970s and have been widely adopted, including by the European Union in 2003, which mandated IFRS for all publicly accountable companies starting in 2005. However, when it comes to IPSAS, these standards were introduced in 2001 by IFAC through its International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board (IPSASB). Although the European Union has not required member states to adopt IPSAS, it encourages them to use these standards to enhance the quality of financial reporting and public financial management, especially in the context of expansion and reform processes in EU candidate countries.

The European Commission is working on developing European Public Sector Accounting Standards (EPSAS) based on IPSAS, but this initiative faces challenges due to political, historical, and cultural differences among member states (Polzer and Reichard, 2019). Some research suggests that IPSAS-based accounting systems may not significantly contribute to the convergence between Governmental Accounting and National Accounts, raising doubts about their effectiveness in reconciling these two systems (Jorge *et al.* 2016). Nevertheless, most EU countries have committed to adopting IPSAS as part of public sector reform, aiming to improve the quality of reports, financial accountability, transparency, and reduce corruption levels at the national level.

Corruption in the public sector is a negative social phenomenon with substantial adverse economic consequences. This issue affects both transition and developed countries. Corruption in the public sector is a persistent global challenge that undermines government credibility and economic stability (Heath, 2000). It is commonly defined as the misuse of government power or resources for private gain (Dunlop and Radaelli, 2019; Bauer, 2000). Corruption can take various forms, including bribery, nepotism, and conflicts of interest (Grobler and Joubert, 2004). Corruption increases the level of externalities in the public sector, reduces citizens' trust in elected political representatives, and negatively impacts citizens' willingness to pay taxes and public revenues to the state. Corruption reduces transparency to conceal the accountability of public management. Transparency involves ensuring that all treasury management activities are conducted openly and can be comprehensively justified, providing the community with full visibility into resource management practices. It emphasizes the obligation of government entities to operate transparently, enabling the public to access information and evaluate the integrity and efficiency of administrative actions. Transparency means open access for all people to all related information (Adil *et al.* 2022). Enhancing transparency and accountability necessitates active citizen participation, as governments are more inclined to take responsibility for their actions when individuals actively seek information on public matters and engage in oversight activities (Fung, 2015). The aim of this study is to fill a research gap by analyzing data from 147 countries to evaluate how the choice of accounting basis and financial reporting framework influences the public sector's reputation for integrity. This research not only provides empirical evidence of the influence of accounting practices on the CPI but also offers a global overview of current trends in public sector accounting and reporting practices. By examining the relationship between accounting standards and corruption perception, this study seeks to contribute to ongoing discussions on the importance of implementing effective accounting systems to strengthen integrity and trust in the public sector.

The paper is divided into three sections: a review of previous research on this topic to highlight differences in research methodologies, followed by research hypotheses with descriptions of indicators and data sources, and finally, the research findings and discussion.

2. The impact of accounting practices on the level of corruption in the public sector

A large number of authors assert that there is a direct link between the accounting system and the level of corruption in countries. For instance, Ghaffoori (2016) highlights that his research findings suggest a decline in corruption levels when governments advance public-sector accounting reforms, implement accrual-based accounting, or adopt IPSAS. Furthermore, an efficient accounting system is considered one of the most effective strategies for combating corruption. Similarly, Cuadrado-Ballesteros *et al.* (2020) found that IPSAS implementation and the adoption of accrual accounting in OECD countries led to a decrease in corruption by enhancing transparency. Their findings revealed a decrease in corruption as governments progressed with public-sector accounting reforms, embraced IPSAS, or transitioned to accrual-based accounting systems. Hamed-Sidhom *et al.* (2022) found that adopting IPSAS plays a significant role in shaping perceptions of corruption, offering vital evidence that highlights transparency as a key factor, especially in underdeveloped countries. Their research indicates that IPSAS is the preferred accounting framework for budget users operating on an accrual basis, contributing to the reduction of corruption within the public sector.

Some authors have focused on studying the impact of IPSAS implementation on the level of corruption in the public sector, with a particular emphasis on developing countries. Tawiah (2021) investigates whether IPSAS represents a potential driver or barrier to corruption in developing countries. Employing a generalized method of moments system on a dataset of 77 developing countries spanning 2005 to 2017, the study demonstrated a significant negative relationship between IPSAS adoption and corruption, indicating that implementing IPSAS helps mitigate corruption in developing nations. This relationship remained consistent even after considering the duration of IPSAS adoption and the implementation of other international accounting standards. Further analysis revealed that the anti-corruption effects of IPSAS were more substantial in countries that fully adopted accrual-based IPSAS. Similarly, Ghaffoori (2016) suggested that reforming accounting processes in Kurdistan could increase accountability and reduce corruption. Likewise, the study by Hamed-Sidhom and Loukil (2021) explored the link between IPSAS adoption and perceived corruption levels in developing countries, with a focus on the mediating influence of political stability. The results reveal that the adoption of IPSAS may not bring about a rapid reduction in perceived corruption. Additionally, they reveal that while political stability helps reduce corruption, it does not enhance the effect of IPSAS adoption on the perceived level of corruption. This study is important as it points to different results compared to most other studies.

Some authors have researched how the introduction of IPSAS impacts improvements in transparency and public accountability, which indirectly influences the reduction of corruption. According to Babatunde (2019), the results of his study indicate that the application of IPSAS significantly enhances transparency and accountability in Nigeria's public sector. Using primary data collected through a survey of 255 accountants and auditors, the study applies multivariate regression analysis to demonstrate that implementing these standards positively impacts the reduction of corruption. Lewis and Hendrawan (2020) argue that the shift from cash-based to accrual-based accounting brings about a notable improvement in financial reporting, empowering citizens to demand greater accountability from the government and curbing the potential for corruption.

Additionally, some authors have investigated the impact of the applied accounting framework and reporting basis on the level of financial accountability and fiscal transparency in budget institutions. The study conducted by Abimola *et al.* (2017) focused on determining the impact of IPSAS implementation on financial accountability in the public sector, measured through the levels of corruption, transparency, and accountability. The research was carried out by examining the views of accounting professionals, and it was found that they believe IPSAS implementation increases transparency and accountability while reducing corruption in Nigeria's

public sector. This implies that Nigeria's economy would be in a better state if IPSAS were fully adopted and implemented. Kartiko *et al.* (2018) conducted a study focused on evaluating the measurement of accrual-based IPSAS implementation by governments and analyzing its connection to fiscal transparency at the central government level. By employing content analysis and Confirmatory Factor Analysis on data from 77 countries, the research highlighted the significance of financial performance statements and accrual accounting policies—such as exchange and non-exchange transactions—as central elements defining accrual implementation levels. The findings, derived from panel data regression, demonstrated that accrual level scores align with external validity, evidenced by their positive correlation with the fiscal transparency index of the International Budget Partnership (IBP). These results underline the importance of a strategic approach for central governments in adopting accrual-based IPSAS. Castaneda (2022), analyzing cross-sectional data from more than 70 countries, discovered that factors like the extent of citizen political engagement and the level of media freedom play a more significant role in explaining variations in fiscal transparency and accountability than the implementation level of IPSAS. This study is significant as it presents contrasting results to previous studies.

Some authors highlight the positive correlation between the implementation of the accrual accounting basis and the effectiveness of financial reporting in the public sector. Kartika *et al.* (2020) presented findings that highlight an empirical model demonstrating how the implementation of an accrual-based system influences the efficiency and effectiveness of financial reporting in the public sector. Using Partial Least Squares for analysis, the study gathered data from 63 internal auditors affiliated with the Finance and Development Supervisory Agency in Central Java, Indonesia. The results showed a significant positive relationship between accrual-based system adoption and improvements in both the efficiency and effectiveness of public sector financial reporting. Gebreyesus (2021) further states that IPSAS has a positive impact on ensuring the relevance and fair presentation of balance sheet positions in financial statements, which can lead to better management and improved resource efficiency in the public sector for the benefit of the community.

Yassine *et al.* (2024) demonstrated that adopting IPSAS significantly enhances the quality and transparency of financial reporting within the public sector. These standards, designed specifically for public sector entities, offer improved information for financial management, accountability, and decision-making processes. By strengthening the reliability of financial reporting, IPSAS supports better resource allocation decisions and plays a vital role in fostering greater financial transparency and accountability.

In conclusion, a significant body of research supports the benefits of implementing IPSAS and the accrual accounting basis in increasing transparency, efficiency, fiscal discipline, and accountability within the public sector.

3. Research methodology, objectives, and data sources

The paper explores the impact of the applied financial reporting framework and the accounting basis on the perception of corruption in the public sector. The research is conducted across 147 countries worldwide, with data used for the analysis referring to the year 2023. The following working hypotheses are tested in the paper:

H1: The implementation of the "International Public Sector Accounting Standards" framework influences the reduction of corruption perception in the public sector, indicated by a higher CPI index value.

H2: The adoption of the accrual accounting basis influences the reduction of corruption perception in the public sector, indicated by a higher CPI index value.

The level of corruption perception in the public sector is measured by the Corruption Perceptions Index (CPI). CPI measures the perception of the level of corruption in the public sector across different countries. It was developed by Transparency International and is published annually. Each country is assigned a score on a scale from 0 to 100, where 0 represents a high level of corruption, and 100 signifies a very low perception of corruption.

Each country's score is a combination of at least three data sources drawn from 13 different corruption surveys and assessments. Transparency International uses a composite index to measure the level of corruption perception in the public sector worldwide for the purpose of comparing them both spatially and temporally. The data sources for calculating the composite index come from relevant institutions that have a supervisory function in their field of operation. Some of these institutions include the World Justice Project, the Economist Intelligence Unit, the World Bank, the African Development Bank, and others. This composite index is regularly tested for its alignment and calibration of the weights of individual indicators in the index to ensure its relevance. The latest test of the index was conducted in 2017 by the Joint Research Centre-JRC (Alvarez Diaz *et al.* 2018). The process of calculating the CPI is regularly reviewed to ensure it remains as robust and coherent as possible.

To determine the financial reporting framework and accounting basis applied in various countries around the world, we used data from IFAC (International Federation of Accountants). IFAC publishes data on the Public Sector Financial Accountability Index. This data verifies and analyses the current financial reporting bases and frameworks used by federal and central governments globally. These data are published periodically, considering that changes in the regulatory framework for financial reporting and accounting bases cannot be quickly altered in practice across countries.

Hypothesis testing was conducted using one-way analysis of variance, considering that the independent variable does not have a numerical value. Additionally, a descriptive statistical analysis is provided in the study regarding the number of countries applying specific variants of accounting regulations for financial reporting by budgetary users.

4. Research results and discussion

4.1. Descriptive analysis

If we examine the representation of individual countries based on the type of accounting framework used for public sector financial reporting (Figure 1), we conclude that the most prevalent framework is national accounting standards, accounting for 41%, followed by national accounting standards referencing IPSAS, with a share of 25%.

Figure 1. Overview of applied accounting frameworks for public sector reporting

Source: Author's processing

If we examine the distribution of accounting bases used for public sector financial reporting (Figure 2), it can be concluded that the partial accrual basis predominates with 42.86%, followed by the cash basis with 29.25%, and the full accrual basis with 27.89%.

Figure 2. Overview of applied accounting bases in the public sector

Source: Author's processing

The full application of IPSAS without modifications, using the accrual accounting basis, is only present in three countries: the Philippines (CPI 34), the Dominican Republic (CPI 35), and Tanzania (40). These countries have above-average levels of corruption in the public sector, as expressed by the corruption perception index. Nine countries use IPSAS without modifications along with the partial accrual accounting basis: Seychelles, Barbados, Costa Rica, Grenada, Rwanda, Kazakhstan, Serbia, Malawi, Kenya, Honduras, and Burundi. Nineteen countries apply IPSAS without modifications using the cash basis, including countries such as Cyprus, Malaysia, Pakistan, Palestine, Libya, the Central African Republic, Zambia, Nicaragua, and others. From this, we can observe that although IPSAS are primarily based on the accrual basis, they represent a flexible framework for financial reporting that recognizes that the transition from the cash basis to the accrual basis may require time and resources. Countries with limited capacity in the public sector or weaker infrastructure often lack the technical or administrative resources needed to implement the accrual basis. For this reason, there is a special accounting framework, "Cash Basis IPSAS," which provides guidelines for countries that are not yet ready for full implementation of the accrual basis. Cash Basis IPSAS was created in response to practical challenges faced by countries with lower levels of economic development or weaker institutional capacities. Its main purpose is to facilitate simple and clear reporting of cash flows, establish a foundation for transparent and accountable public financial management, and serve as a preparatory step for transitioning to the accrual accounting basis.

Countries that use national accounting standards for budgetary users with the accrual accounting basis include the United States of America, Canada, Argentina, France, Belgium, Finland, Denmark, Japan, China, Moldova, and others. Countries that apply national accounting standards with the partial accrual accounting basis include Italy, Romania, Slovenia, Poland, Hungary, Croatia, Bulgaria, Albania, Belarus, and others. Countries that use national accounting standards for budgetary users with the cash accounting basis include Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Ireland, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Malta, Singapore, India, Saudi Arabia, and others.

An interesting fact is that there are two countries that apply national accounting standards based on IFRS, and both use the accrual accounting basis. These countries are the United Kingdom and Australia. In the UK, the public sector reporting framework is the IFRS-based Financial Reporting Manual (FRoM). It is aligned with IFRS but further adapted for specifics such as public services, asset management, subsidies, and grants. The Australian public sector uses IFRS-based standards adapted for budgetary users through the framework known as the Australian Accounting Standards Board's Public Sector Reporting Requirements (AASB). This accounting framework provides a foundation for consistent and reliable financial reporting at all levels of government in Australia, from local communities to federal institutions. It also allows for adaptability to the specific needs of the public sector, while ensuring compliance with global accounting practices.

In the sample of 147 countries, 93, or 61.22%, have a corruption perception index below 50, meaning these countries are perceived as highly corrupt. Among them, 8 countries, or 5.44%, have a CPI value lower than 20. The countries considered the most corrupt (with the lowest CPI values) in the sample are Somalia (11), South Sudan (13), Korea (17), Haiti (17), Nicaragua (17), Burundi (20), Chad (20), and Tajikistan (20). On the other hand, the countries with the lowest corruption perception (the highest CPI values) are Denmark (90), Finland (87), New Zealand (85), Norway (84), Singapore (83), Sweden (82), and Switzerland (82).

4.2. Results of hypothesis testing

We tested whether the adoption of the accounting framework "International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS)" influences a lower Corruption Perception (indicated by a higher CPI index value) in the public sector worldwide. The results of the testing are provided in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics – reporting accounting framework

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
National standards: other	60	3011	50.1833	361.7794
National standards with reference to IPSAS	36	1533	42.5833	302.1929
National standards based on IFRS	2	146	73	8
IPSAS with no modifications	34	1316	38.7059	201.1836
IPSAS modified for the local context	15	721	48.0667	490.6381

Source: Author's processing

Table 2. Results of One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	4792.941	4	1198.235	3.7447	0.0063	2.4354
Within Groups	45437.73	142	319.984			
Total	50230.67	146				

Source: Author's processing

The obtained p-value is 0.0063, which is below the usual significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the adoption of different accounting frameworks is associated with differences in the Corruption Perception Index (CPI). The F-statistic value (3.7447) is greater than the critical value (2.4354), which confirms the presence of significant differences between the groups. The variation between groups is 4792.941, showing that the choice of accounting framework influences the perception of corruption. However, a larger portion of the total variation (45437.73) belongs to the variation within the groups, implying that factors other than the choice of accounting framework (e.g., political stability, management transparency, legal system, etc.) also affect the perception of corruption.

Countries that use national standards based on IFRS show the lowest level of perceived corruption in the public sector. On the other hand, countries that use IPSAS without modifications have the highest level of perceived corruption in the public sector. This suggests that IPSAS, in its original form, is not necessarily associated with a lower level of corruption, contrary to claims made in many previous studies included in the presented research.

We tested whether the adoption of an accrual accounting basis influences a lower corruption perception (indicated by a higher CPI index value) in the public sector. The results of the testing are provided in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics – accounting basis

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Accrual	41	2271	55.3902	425.9939
Cash	43	1853	43.0930	334.2292
Partial Accrual	63	2592	41.1429	224.2857

Source: Author's processing

Table 4. Results of One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	5450.507	2	2725.253	8.7241	0.0003	3.0589
Within Groups	44983.098	144	312.382			
Total	50433.605	146				

Source: Author's processing

We can conclude that the F-value (8.72) is greater than the critical F-value (F crit = 3.06), indicating that the difference between the observed groups is statistically significant. The p-value (0.00027) is smaller than the standard significance level of 0.05, suggesting that there is a statistically significant difference between the observed groups.

Based on the results of the ANOVA analysis, we can conclude that there is a statistically significant difference in the average values of the corruption perception index between countries using different accounting bases (accrual, cash, and partial accrual). This result indicates that the choice of accounting basis may have an impact on the perception of corruption in the public sector. Countries with an accrual basis have the highest average corruption perception index (55.39), indicating the lowest levels of perceived corruption. This suggests that the adoption of accrual accounting may be associated with improved perceptions of corruption control. On the other hand, countries using a cash basis and partial accrual basis exhibit lower average CPI values, with the partial accrual basis showing the lowest CPI value (41.14), which may imply a less favorable impact of this accounting basis on reducing corruption.

5. Conclusion

Based on the conducted research, we can conclude that the adoption of different accounting frameworks in the public sector, as well as the choice of accounting basis, has a significant impact on the level of perceived corruption (measured by the CPI index). The results of the ANOVA analysis indicate a statistically significant difference in corruption perception indices among countries using accrual, cash, and partial accrual bases.

Although it was expected that the application of the accrual basis in combination with IPSAS standards would reduce the perception of corruption, the results show that countries with accrual basis, along with national accounting standards, have a lower corruption perception (higher CPI index value). These findings suggest that simpler reporting frameworks and accrual bases may be associated with greater transparency and lower perceptions of corruption in the public sector. On the other hand, more complex frameworks, such as IPSAS or national standards with reference to IPSAS, combined with a cash basis and partial accrual basis, do not necessarily contribute to reducing corruption perception in the public sector. Countries that use national standards based on IFRS show the lowest level of perceived corruption in the public sector (the highest CPI value).

The limitations of the conducted research include several factors that may impact the accuracy and generalizability of the results. First and foremost, the research relied on secondary data concerning the corruption perception index and accounting practices. Additionally, the political, economic, and social contexts of the countries using different accounting practices may influence the results, and these factors were not considered in the analysis. While ANOVA was employed to analyze differences among the groups, causality between accounting practices and corruption perception has not been directly proven, which warrants further investigation. Furthermore, small sample sizes in some groups, such as those using national standards based on IFRS, may reduce the statistical power of the tests.

The results of this study contribute to the existing literature examining the relationship between accounting practices and corruption perception in the public sector, but partially diverge from the findings of previous studies. Earlier research often emphasized that the adoption of accrual accounting and international standards, such as IPSAS, contributes to greater transparency and accountability, which should reduce corruption. However, the results

of our study suggest that countries which apply simpler accounting frameworks for financial reporting by budgetary users, such as national standards and IPSAS modified to the local context, have a lower level of corruption perception, as measured by a higher CPI value.

These findings imply that more complex accounting frameworks may not provide the expected benefits in combating corruption in all contexts and that factors such as institutional capacity and political will may prove more influential than the accounting standards themselves. This discrepancy highlights the need for further research that incorporates a broader range of variables and more thoroughly examines the contextual factors specific to individual countries.

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